

Practice Abstract no. 49

FOODITY - Open Call #2 project - MyNutri

The FOODITY project launched the second of its two open calls in May 2024 and closed in July 2024. The FOODITY project selected six innovative data-driven projects that develop solutions contributing to more sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty. Starting in November 2024, the six projects will receive up to €187,500 to develop their project activities.

One of the selected projects is “MyNutri: AI-based personalised health scores of food products based on consumers’ health concerns.”

Profile

Project acronym / title	MyNutri AI-based personalised health scores of food products based on consumers’ health concerns
Partners (country)	Tellspec SAS (France), Centro Nacional de Tecnología y Seguridad Alimentaria (Spain)
Project area	Shopping experiences

Context

The MyNutri project has the mission to enable citizens to make educated and individualised decisions when purchasing their food, and to improve individual eating habits and ethical food consumption by providing customised insights on food products based on a set of users’ health concerns.

The MyNutri solution empowers citizens to make informed decisions during their shopping experience that are customised to their health profile and that can also be sustainable food choices. Through the solution, citizens can take a photo of the product being considered for purchase and it will deliver two scores: (1) an individualised health score and (2) a carbon footprint score. Unlike other applications, the health score is not based only on the food’s ingredients, but is AI-generated to best match the user’s health profile, which are identified through a preliminary and subsequent health questionnaires. The health profile may include parameters such as age, exercise levels, health concerns such as allergies or metabolic issues, genetic/genome profile, microbiome information, and food consumption habits.

This customisation is valuable because a specific food/ ingredient may be beneficial for one person but cause problems to another. For instance, tofu, a good protein source and meat alternative, should be limited by those with thyroid disorders, as it is a goitrogen and interferes with normal thyroid function.

The MyNutri technology relies on a searchable database of more than 2,500 food ingredients, developed by Telspec over the past 11 years, and partly available at [Telspecopedia.com](https://telspecopedia.com). This database provides education, based on scientific evidence, on food and its ingredients including additives, contaminants, and manufacturing by-products.

Objectives

The main objectives of the MyNutri project are:

1. **Develop and test the MyNutri application**, an Android app, by following a user-centred approach and involving selected end-users throughout the entire process. The app will include the current Telspecopedia mobile app and its database of ingredients.
2. **Develop the MyNutri Dataset** to categorise users based on their health concerns, and develop the Health Score AI models to predict the personalised health score of food products based on their ingredients, the users health concerns, and the user's food consumption over time.
3. **Develop educational content based on the current Telspectopedia asset**, which has the twofold aim to educate users on the actual healthiness of labelled food products through enhanced knowledge of the ingredients and their health effect, and to generate awareness in users about the use of their health data, how to protect them, and how they can become crucial to improve their decision-making process when buying and consuming food products.
4. **Design a comprehensive launch program and business plan** for the market launch of the application. The objective is to consolidate the business plan for the commercialisation, the route to the market and marketing strategy, starting with a free version of the app which will evolve into a freemium business model with the organic growth of the user base.

Impact

MyNutri is expected to generate the following impacts:

- **Promotion of healthier dietary decisions based on scientific evidence:** The MyNutri project empowers citizens to make healthier food choices by providing them with food products' health score based on their ingredients and specific health concerns. This personalised health score helps users decide whether to purchase a product and suggests better alternatives if available, thus ensuring they can make informed decisions that align with their health needs and dietary restrictions.
- **Citizens' empowerment to drive market demand and food production:** If users consistently choose healthier products based on MyNutri's recommendations, they can collectively influence food producers and retailers. This citizen-driven demand can encourage the development and

supply of healthier and more sustainable food options. Analysing aggregated data regarding user choices can offer relevant insights into consumer preferences. This data-driven feedback loop encourages food producers to adjust their products, meeting the demand for healthier and more sustainable options.

- **User sovereignty over their data and data usage for users' benefit:** MyNutri ensures that user data is used solely to benefit the user, without leveraging personal data for targeted advertising or third-party sales. The app's main focus is on enhancing user health and promoting sustainability, thereby fostering user trust and engagement.
- **Users' data right protection and awareness:** MyNutri is committed to protecting users' data rights by adhering to GDPR regulations. This includes implementing data anonymisation, pseudonymisation, encryption, and rigorous privacy practices. Additionally, MyNutri educates users about their data rights, enhancing their awareness and understanding of how their data is collected, used, and protected. By educating users about their data rights and the privacy measures in place, MyNutri empowers them to make informed decisions about their data.
- **Diseases' prevention and contrast:** MyNutri contributes to the prevention and management of diet-related diseases. Specifically, it empowers citizens with existing health conditions to select healthier food choices. Poor diet is a known contributor to numerous chronic illnesses, including cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and cancer. Through the delivery of personalised health scores and suggested superior alternatives, MyNutri actively assists users in making dietary decisions that mitigate the development and progression of these health issues.

